

TECHNICAL EVALUATION OF A STAND-ALONE PV HEAT PUMP SYSTEM FOR SPACE HEATING/COOLING APPLICATIONS WITHOUT BATTERIES

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ABSTRACT: In the last years, the concept of solar photovoltaic (PV) powered heat pumps (HP) has become very attractive, in order to match the increasing heating/cooling demand with a renewable and environmentally-friendly energy source. The objective of this work is to technically validate a stand-alone PV-HP system for space heating/cooling applications. This paper describes the prototype system installed in Madrid (Spain) for this purpose, together with the definition of the validation tests to be performed. Finally, some modifications are proposed for the performance indicators that are traditionally used for comparing HP and PV systems, in order to achieve a characterization that is more specific to PV-powered systems.

Keywords: Evaluation, Heat Pump, Stand-alone PV system, Performance

1 INTRODUCTION

Space heating and cooling, both for residential and industrial applications, is a highly energy consuming activity that needs to meet increasing electricity demands along the whole planet. Heat pumps help to reduce significantly the electricity consumption required to cover thermal necessities, so they are becoming an increasingly important technology. In Europe, the heat pump market increased by 12% in terms of units sold in 2015 (which means an installed electrical power of 2.11 GW) [1] and by 12% in 2016 (2.37 GW) [2]. This market growth is expected to be maintained in the near future, with estimations of the compound annual growth rate in the range 6.02% [3] to 10.25% [4] for the period 2016-2021. However, in most cases the electricity consumed by a heat-pump system is obtained directly from the national grid or from stand-alone generation sets (mostly diesel generators). Solar thermal heat pumps, that use solar collectors as the evaporator of the system, have been widely explored and demonstrated: they reduce the electricity consumption of the heat pump, but they do not guarantee that such electricity is generated by a renewable source. Consequently, latest research on solar heat pumps is focused on the use of Photovoltaic (PV) generators for powering the variable-speed compressor that circulates the refrigerant loop [5], [6], [7].

The objective of this work is to technically validate a stand-alone PV Heat Pump (PV-HP) system for space heating and cooling applications, where the variable-speed compressor of the heat pump is directly powered by a PV array through a frequency inverter. Such validation implies to manage the power intermittences due to cloud passing and to minimize the day/night generation cycle problem. The validation test scheduling is presented. Finally, some modifications of the traditional performance indicators are proposed, in order to adapt them to PV-powered systems.

2 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

For performing the technical validation of a stand-alone heat pump system without batteries, a PV-HP prototype has been installed at the IES-UPM building. Figure 1 shows the schematic of this prototype. It

consists of a PV generator with two possible configurations (one of 1.6 kW and another of 3.6 kW) that powers a 1.5 kW air-to-air heat pump through a 4 kW frequency inverter. The heat pump external unit is placed at a small thermally isolated room, which simulates the ambient. The internal unit is placed at a similar room that simulates the space to be heated or cooled. Two auxiliary grid-powered heat pumps (also air-to-air) have been installed in these two rooms for temperature control: the effect of the PV-HP can be accelerated or countered for simulating different testing conditions (i.e winter/summer ambient conditions or different thermal loads). Figure 2 shows the main components of the system described: PV generator, frequency inverter, interior room and exterior room.

Figure 1: Schematic of the PV-HP prototype installed at the IES-UPM building in Madrid, Spain.

Figure 2: Images of the PV-HP prototype installed in Madrid (Spain), composed of the PV generator (a), frequency inverter (b), interior room (c) and exterior room (d).

3 VALIDATION TESTS

3.1 Characterization with the electric grid

Before powering the compressor of the HP with a PV generator, it was characterized using the electric grid and the internal control plate of the HP. The objective of this test was to learn the frequency/temperature characteristics of the compressor, in order to replicate the logic of the control plate with the frequency inverter.

Figure 3 shows the results of a test performed at constant T_{ext} , both in cooling (a) and heating modes (b). The input frequency of the compressor depends on ΔT , which is the difference between T_{int} and the temperature set point. It can be observed that the frequency increases almost instantly to its maximum value at the beginning of the test. As ΔT is reduced, so is the frequency of the compressor, until the temperature set point is reached.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Results of the frequency/temperature characterization of the compressor using the electric grid and the internal control plate of the HP, for the cooling (a) and heating (b) modes.

3.2 Technical validation with the PV generator

The technical validation of the PV-HP system described in section 2 will be performed through a series of experiments, designed for simulating different operating conditions:

- The PV generator can be programmed to operate always at its Maximum Power Point (MPP), using all the available PV electricity for powering the compressor of the HP. Another possibility is to operate at a point of the I-V curve where the PV output is exactly the electricity demanded by the compressor for reaching a certain temperature in the interior room. This operation point will not be necessarily the MPP.
- There are two possible configurations for the PV array, resulting into two different nominal powers of 1.1 kW (undersized generator) and 3 kW (oversized generator).
- The HP performance is highly affected by the temperature conditions in both the interior and exterior rooms (T_{int} and T_{ext} respectively). The auxiliary grid-powered heat pumps can be used for controlling these temperatures. Usually, T_{int} is kept constant at a given set value (different for heating and cooling modes). On the other hand, T_{ext} can be kept constant or follow a certain daily profile (different for winter or summer conditions). When operating in heating mode, winter conditions will be simulated and vice versa.

The combination of different operating conditions results into the following 8 validation tests:

Table I: Operating conditions for all the validation tests here proposed.

	PV Operation Point	PV generator configuration	Temperature conditions
T1	MPP	Undersized	T_{int} and T_{ext} constant
T2	MPP	Undersized	T_{int} constant, T_{ext} variable
T3	MPP	Oversized	T_{int} and T_{ext} constant
T4	MPP	Oversized	T_{int} constant, T_{ext} variable
T5	Not MPP	Undersized	T_{int} and T_{ext} constant
T6	Not MPP	Undersized	T_{int} constant, T_{ext} variable
T7	Not MPP	Oversized	T_{int} and T_{ext} constant
T8	Not MPP	Oversized	T_{int} constant, T_{ext} variable

4 PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

4.1 Traditional performance indicators

The performance of HP systems, in terms of how efficiently they transform electrical energy into thermal energy, is typically evaluated through the Coefficient of Performance (COP) when operating in heating mode or through the Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER) when operating in cooling mode. These indicators are defined as follows:

$$COP = \frac{Q_c}{W_{com}} \quad (1)$$

$$EER = \frac{Q_e}{W_{com}} \quad (2)$$

where Q_c is the heating power of the condenser in heating mode, Q_e is the cooling power of the evaporator in cooling mode and W_{com} is the electric power consumed by the compressor.

The performance of a PV generator is usually evaluated through the Performance Ratio (PR), which represents the ratio between the PV energy that is actually generated and the PV energy that could have been ideally generated for a certain period of time:

$$PR = \frac{E_{PV}}{\frac{P^*}{G^*} \int G(t) dt} \quad (3)$$

where E_{PV} is the useful (meaning that it is either used for powering the compressor, for charging a battery or exported to the grid) DC energy produced by the PV generator, P^* is the nominal power of the PV generator, G^* is the solar irradiance under Standard Test Conditions (STC) and G is the solar irradiance received in the plane of the PV generator.

Finally, when a PV generator is connected to any electric load different from the grid (i.e. a heat pump), the Self-Consumption Ratio (SCR) and the PV Penetration Rate (PVPR) evaluate the quality of the coupling between both systems. For a PV-HP, these indicators are given by the following equations:

$$SCR = \frac{E_{PV.com}}{E_{PV}} \quad (4)$$

$$PVPR = \frac{E_{PV.com}}{E_{com}} \quad (5)$$

where $E_{PV.com}$ is the PV energy consumed at the compressor of the HP, both directly or after being stored in a battery, and E_{com} is the total electric energy consumed by the compressor of the HP, regardless of how it is generated.

4.2 Modified performance indicators for PV-HP systems

When approaching the performance evaluation of a PV-HP system, a combination of the aforementioned indicators would help to integrate three different characteristics of the system: the quality of the heat pump

(characterized by the COP or the EER), the quality of the PV generator (characterized by the PR), and the quality of the integration of the two systems (characterized by the SCR and the PVPR).

In this work, an adapted COP for PV-HP systems is proposed:

$$COP_{PV-HP} = COP(1 + PR \times SCR \times PVPR) \quad (6)$$

COP_{PV-HP} will be equal to the traditional COP if there is no PV energy generation and/or use ($PR=SCR=PVPR=0$); COP_{PV-HP} will double the traditional COP if the PV generator performs ideally and all its electricity production is used for powering the compressor, with no excess to be exported to the grid ($PR=1, SCR=1, PVPR=1$).

Similarly, the adapted EER_{PV-HP} is defined as follows:

$$EER_{PV-HP} = EER(1 + PR \times SCR \times PVPR) \quad (7)$$

This indicator will also present values in the range of 1 to 2 times the value of the traditional EER.

Finally, some considerations must be accounted when calculating the PR. As traditionally defined, this indicator is highly affected by factors that do not depend on the quality of the PV system, such as the heating/cooling period, the daily heating/cooling demand profile or possible failures of the compressor or any of the components of the heat pump. For separating these external factors from those that are strictly related to the PV generator performance, the PR can be factorized by distinguishing between irradiation losses for three essentially different reasons: the non-heating/cooling period, the intrinsic characteristics of the PV-HP system design and the external factors:

$$PR = \frac{E_{PV}}{P^*/G^*} \times \frac{1}{\int G dt} \times \frac{\int_{HCp} G dt}{\int_{HCp} G dt} \times \frac{\int G_{useful} dt}{\int G_{useful} dt} \times \frac{\int G_{used} dt}{\int G_{used} dt} \quad (8)$$

where HCp is the heating/cooling period determined by the particular application, G_{useful} is the available useful irradiance during the HCp determined by the relationship between the P^* , the PV generator structure and the type of heating/cooling system that will determine the power requirements throughout the day, and G_{used} is the irradiance effectively used by the system. To clarify these concepts, G_{HCp} , G_{useful} , and G_{used} are shown in Figure 4 for a hypothetical constant power heat-pump system. It can be shown that G_{HCp} is the total irradiance during the heating/cooling period determined by a certain application (Figure 4-a). G_{useful} is the irradiance required to deliver the constant power required by a certain heat pump (Figure 4-b). It is worth noting that with irradiances below G_{useful} the heat pump will not be able to work because the power required will not be reached, and irradiances higher than G_{useful} will be partially wasted because the system works at constant power. Finally, G_{used} is the part of G_{useful} that has been used effectively as a result of the scheduling of heating/cooling selected by the end-user (Figure 4-c). In this last figure, the irradiance from 7 am to 14 pm was wasted because of the heating/cooling scheduling rather than technical problems in the PV system.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: Graphical representation of the different irradiations considered: (a) $\int G_{HCp}$ is the irradiation during the heating/cooling period (HCp), (b) $\int G_{useful}$ is the useful irradiation during the HCp determined by the design of the PV HP system; and (c) $\int G_{used}$ is the irradiation used effectively by the system.

So, it is possible to rewrite equation (8) as:

$$PR = PR_{PV} \times UR_{HCp} \times UR_{PVHP} \times UR_{EF} \quad (9)$$

where:

$PR_{PV} = \frac{E_{PV}}{P^*/G^*} \times \frac{1}{\int G_{used} dt}$	This is the PR considering only losses strictly associated to the PV system itself, i.e., actual versus
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	nominal peak power, dirtiness, thermal and DC/AC conversion losses. It is intrinsic to the technical quality of the PV component and its maintenance.
$UR_{HCp} = \frac{\int_{HCp} G dt}{\int G dt}$	This is the ratio of the total irradiation throughout the HCp period to the total annual irradiation (Fig. 4-a). It is intrinsic to a given application of heating/cooling. Note that it can only be applied to the annual period.
$UR_{PVHP} = \frac{\int G_{useful} dt}{\int_{HCp} G dt}$	This is the ratio of the irradiation necessary to deliver the power required by the heat pump to the total irradiation throughout the HCp (Fig. 4-b). It is intrinsic to the heating/cooling system design; specifically it depends on the type of heating/cooling system (at constant or at variable power), the ratio between the PV peak power and the PV power required for heating/cooling, and on the tracking geometry.
$UR_{EF} = \frac{\int G_{used} dt}{\int G_{useful} dt}$	This is the ratio of the irradiation required by the heat pump during the heating/cooling scheduling to the same irradiation during the HCp.

The modified performance indicators here proposed (COP_{PV-HP} , EER_{PV-HP} and PR factorized) will be evaluated for the PV-HP prototype described in section 2, for all the validation tests specified in section 3. It must be noted that $PVPR=1$ for this study, as corresponding to a stand-alone system. However, this indicator must be taken into account for hybrid PV/grid configurations.

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